

Information of the Extended Abstract

TITLE: *Multi-Scale Fibre-Optic Sensing Experiments for Subsurface Monitoring*

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Statement

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Introduction

High-resolution distributed fibre-optic sensing (DFOS) offers a crucial advantage by enabling data acquisition with significantly higher spatial resolution and, in many cases, a broader frequency bandwidth than conventional sensors, while maintaining accuracy across multiple spatial and temporal scales. This enables the early detection of subsurface integrity problems and induced seismicity across various scales, thereby enhancing operational safety, reducing costs, and fostering public trust in geothermal and energy storage projects. Yet the detailed character and fidelity of its signals remain poorly quantified and are frequently overlooked.

This work presents a comprehensive, multi-scale experimental campaign designed to quantify the limitations of DFOS and establish validated protocols that bridge the gap between laboratory studies and field applications. Within the framework of EPOS-eNLarge, by integrating facilities and expertise from Utrecht University, TU Delft, the TNO Rijswijk Centre for Sustainable Geo-Energy (RCSG), and field sites (the Groningen gas field or the Delft geothermal site), we aim to develop robust methodologies for subsurface DFOS deployment.

Methodology and Experimental Framework

To create reliable strategies for deploying DFOS in the subsurface, we plan to conduct a series of experiments across variable spatial scales, ranging from millimetres to centimetres, decimetres, and metres, followed by field data validation (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Schematic of cross-scale experiments, illustrating variable spatial scales ranging from millimetres to centimetres, decimetres, and metres.

At Utrecht University's HPT laboratory, high-resolution distributed strain sensing (DSS) tests will be conducted on rock cores (heights 20-80 mm; diameters 10-40 mm) under controlled pressure-temperature conditions to capture the evolution of strain during rock deformation. Cylindrical specimens, instrumented with fibre-optic cables of varied coupling and orientation, will be loaded uniaxially in a standard frame until failure (Figure 2a). A laser vibrometer will be employed alongside the DSS setup to monitor surface vibrations during deformation and failure, enabling cross-comparison with distributed strain measurements and providing insights into the acoustic energy associated with micro-fracturing events. The aims are to characterise fracture initiation and propagation, strain localisation, and the fidelity of the recorded DSS signals.

Building upon earlier experiments, at the TU Delft Rock Deformation laboratory, we plan to deploy fibres with multiple orientations on ≈ 0.5 m rock blocks and induce fracture opening in the borehole simulator setup (Figure 2b). In this setup, we will record slow-deformation signals with DSS and attempt to capture acoustic-energy outbursts using distributed acoustic sensing (DAS). With these tests, we will assess static-dynamic response calibration and acoustic-event localisation and will benchmark DSS measurements against DAS.

Figure 2 (a) Experimental setup at HPT lab (Utrecht University) for measuring strain variations during uniaxial loading of a cylindrical rock sample using Distributed Strain Sensing (DSS). (b) The laboratory setup at Rockdef Lab (TU Delft) for DFOS measurements at elevated stress conditions. (c) Illustrative setup at RCSG (TNO) for mounting the cement block in a 400-ton hydraulic press for a monotonic uniaxial compression test, with continuous acquisition of load, displacement, and other sensor data until failure.

To bridge the gap between lab-scale and field-scale deployments, we propose scaling up a small setup to a meter-scale experiment inside the 400-ton uniaxial press at the RCSG. A homogeneous or layered cement sample (1.37 m in diameter and 1.0 m in height, exact dimensions to be confirmed) (Figure 2c) will be used for this test. Multiple small wells will be created either by drilling or as a result of the casting process. Each borehole will be instrumented with fibre optic cables for DSS and DAS for complementary measurement points for data verification purposes. A 400-ton hydraulic press will be used for the uniaxial compression test, with continuous acquisition of load, displacement and other sensor data until failure. During the continuous load-to-failure run, the DSS recordings will resolve millimetre-scale strain localisation and quasi-static strain. At the same time, the DAS measurements capture the kilohertz acoustic-emission bursts associated with rapid crack propagation. This will

enable us to create a seamless strain history at every measurement point, allowing for direct comparison with co-located conventional sensors.

Lastly, field data will be used to validate lab-derived observations and assess the long-term performance of DFOS in operational environments. We will use field data from the Groningen gas field and/or TU Delft's DAP research boreholes.

Expected Outcomes

This multi-scale experimental approach will provide distributed-strain measurements, enabling the systematic evaluation of millimetre-scale strain build-up and localisation that precede rupture, facilitating the location of micro-events, and allowing for the testing of moment-tensor inversion using DAS data. Results will be compared with traditional geophone-based methods to assess the performance of DAS-only localisation. Additionally, with these experiments, we will address the scaling challenge of translating measurements made with a sensor spacing of 0.25 cm in the lab to field-scale deployments, with data recording at 1–2-meter intervals at a gauge length of a few meters.

The expected outcomes of this work include validated DSS/DAS transfer functions under varying stress, temperature, and coupling conditions; benchmarks for DAS-only event localisation and moment tensor inversion; and quantitative relationships between strain evolution, acoustic emissions, and failure modes.

Conclusions

This work presents the first fully integrated lab-to-field workflow for fibre-optic sensing in subsurface applications. Through rigorous validation of DFOS technologies across various spatial scales and sensor types, we establish a robust foundation for interpreting DAS/DSS data, develop scalable sensor deployment strategies, and deliver field-ready benchmarks and calibration protocols. These contributions enable safer and more reliable monitoring of subsurface operations, ultimately supporting and accelerating the energy transition.

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